

Greening European Mobility through Cascading Innovation Initiatives

Thank you very much for your help to the research activities of the **GEMINI project** funded by the **Horizon Europe program of the EU**: <https://www.geminiproject.eu/>. By filling this questionnaire you will contribute to promote a more sustainable mobility in the future.

The objective of this survey is to identify emerging technical and social innovations drivers that could impact the implementation and success of **New and Shared mobility Services**.

The questionnaire is anonymous. The information will be treated according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU.

We are interested in **hearing your independent personal opinion**, which does not have to coincide necessarily with the point of view of the company / government you work for.

The survey will take you around **15 minutes**. It can be filled on a mobile phone, but it is preferable to complete it on a computer or tablet. If you have any questions, please contact us by email at:

Laura Garrido - l.garrido@upm.es
Juan Nicolás González - juannicolas.gonzalez@upm.es

Thank you very much for your cooperation!

RESPONDENT CHARACTERISATION

Definition of New and Shared Mobility Services (NMS)

New and shared mobility can be defined as novel transportation services and resources that are shared among users who do not necessarily know each other in advance, either concurrently or one after another, using digital platforms for supplying and paying for the services. This includes, for example, micromobility (bike sharing, scooter sharing, etc.); shared automobile-based modes (carsharing, ride-hailing, on-demand microtransit, etc.); commute-based modes or ridesharing (carpooling, vanpooling, etc.); and mobility as a service platforms.

* To what extent do you agree with the following sentence: "I consider myself an expert on new and shared mobility services (NMS)"?

Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* Have you ever used new and shared mobility services (NMS)?

- Yes
- No

RESPONDENT CHARACTERISATION

* If you are a user, please state your frequency of use of new and shared mobility services:

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Every once in a while
- Rarely

* Please indicate the new and shared mobility services that you use (select all the options you need):

- Carsharing
- Bike sharing
- Moped scooter sharing
- Kick scooter sharing
- Ride-hailing
- On-demand microtransit
- Ridesharing (carpooling, vanpooling, etc.)
- Maas
- Mobility Hubs
- Other (please specify)

KEY SOCIETAL GOALS

Indicate, in your personal opinion, **how is the general importance for society of the following Key Societal Goals:**

* Economic-related goals

	Not important	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Financial sustainability of governments and businesses	<input type="radio"/>				
Resiliency	<input type="radio"/>				
Keeping prices of essential services at an affordable level	<input type="radio"/>				
Job creation	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion of innovation	<input type="radio"/>				
Productivity gains stemming from reducing congestion and bottlenecks	<input type="radio"/>				

* Social-related goals

	Not important	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Accessibility for people with reduced mobility	<input type="radio"/>				
Accessibility and proximity to goods and services	<input type="radio"/>				
Gender equality	<input type="radio"/>				
Social equity	<input type="radio"/>				
Health improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
Education and training	<input type="radio"/>				
Safety and security	<input type="radio"/>				
Promoting work-life balance	<input type="radio"/>				
Better use of public space in the cities	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of jobs	<input type="radio"/>				

*** Environmental-related goals**

	Not important	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Mitigate climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Improve air quality in cities	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce noise pollution	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce natural resources consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
Promote circular economy	<input type="radio"/>				
Preserve Ecosystem / Biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>				

*** Governance-related goals**

	Not important	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Transparency	<input type="radio"/>				
Democracy	<input type="radio"/>				
Institutional Quality	<input type="radio"/>				
Legal certainty	<input type="radio"/>				
Justice	<input type="radio"/>				

KEY SOCIETAL GOALS

For each pairwise comparison of two sustainability criteria, point out the one which, **in your personal opinion**, is preferable for society. If, for example, you select a **Strong preference for the “economic” criteria over the “environmental” criteria**; you are implicitly claiming that economic criteria are much more important for society than environmental criteria.

* Please state your preference:

Strong Preference Economic Criteria	Weak Preference Economic Criteria	Indifference	Weak Preference Environmental Criteria	Strong Preference Environmental Criteria
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* Please state your preference:

Strong Preference Economic Criteria	Weak Preference Economic Criteria	Indifference	Weak Preference Governance Criteria	Strong Preference Governance Criteria
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* Please state your preference:

Strong Preference Social Criteria	Weak Preference Social Criteria	Indifference	Weak Preference Environmental Criteria	Strong Preference Environmental Criteria
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* Please state your preference:

Strong Preference Environmental Criteria	Weak Preference Environmental Criteria	Indifference	Weak Preference Governance Criteria	Strong Preference Governance Criteria
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

KEY SOCIETAL GOALS

Indicate, in your personal opinion, **to what extent new and shared mobility services will be able to contribute to achieving the following Key Societal Goals:**

* Economic-related goals

	Nothing	Little	Something	Much	Very Much
Financial sustainability of governments and businesses	<input type="radio"/>				
Resiliency	<input type="radio"/>				
Keeping prices of essential services at an affordable level	<input type="radio"/>				
Job creation	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion of innovation	<input type="radio"/>				
Productivity gains stemming from reducing congestion and bottlenecks	<input type="radio"/>				

* Social-related goals

	Nothing	Little	Something	Much	Very Much
Accessibility for people with reduced mobility	<input type="radio"/>				
Accessibility and proximity to goods and services	<input type="radio"/>				
Gender equality	<input type="radio"/>				
Social equity	<input type="radio"/>				
Health improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
Education and training	<input type="radio"/>				
Safety and security	<input type="radio"/>				
Promoting work-life balance	<input type="radio"/>				
Better use of public space	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of jobs	<input type="radio"/>				

*** Environmental-related goals**

	Nothing	Little	Something	Much	Very Much
Mitigate climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Improve air quality in cities	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce noise pollution	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce natural resources consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
Promote circular economy	<input type="radio"/>				
Preserve Ecosystem / Biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>				

Please indicate, in your personal opinion, **the importance of the following Key Governance Goals for the successful implementation of new and shared mobility services:**

*** Governance-related goals**

	Not Important	Slightly Important	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Extremely Important
Transparency	<input type="radio"/>				
Democracy	<input type="radio"/>				
Institutional Quality	<input type="radio"/>				
Legal certainty	<input type="radio"/>				
Justice	<input type="radio"/>				

SOCIAL INNOVATION DRIVERS

* In your personal opinion, **how important are the following social trends nowadays?**

	Not Important	Slightly Important	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Extremely Important
Working from home culture	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>				
Aging of the population	<input type="radio"/>				
Urban sprawl	<input type="radio"/>				
Rural depopulation	<input type="radio"/>				
Digitalization of relationships	<input type="radio"/>				
Immigration growth	<input type="radio"/>				
Sustainability and environmental concerns	<input type="radio"/>				
User's demand for a greater quality of service	<input type="radio"/>				
Increase of sustainable finance	<input type="radio"/>				
Detachment of car ownership	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of social networks	<input type="radio"/>				
Boom of tourism	<input type="radio"/>				
New family models	<input type="radio"/>				

If you consider that there are important social trends that are not reflected in the table above, please include them below.

* Indicate, in your personal opinion, **to what extent the following social trends can influence (positively or negatively) the adoption and frequency of use of new and shared mobility services:**

	Negatively	Somehow Negatively	Nothing	Somehow Positively	Positively
Working from home culture	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>				
Aging of the population	<input type="radio"/>				
Urban sprawl	<input type="radio"/>				
Rural depopulation	<input type="radio"/>				
Digitalization of relationships	<input type="radio"/>				
Immigration growth	<input type="radio"/>				
Sustainability and environmental concerns	<input type="radio"/>				
User's demand for a greater quality of service	<input type="radio"/>				
Increase of sustainable finance	<input type="radio"/>				
Detachment of car ownership	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of social networks	<input type="radio"/>				
Boom of tourism	<input type="radio"/>				
New family models	<input type="radio"/>				

TECHNICAL INNOVATION DRIVERS

* In your opinion, evaluate the potential of the following technology enablers to transform the current mobility landscape.

	Very Low Potential	Low Potential	Moderate Potential	High Potential	Very High Potential
Physical and ICT Infrastructure (Charging Infrastructure, Dedicated lanes, Mobility hubs, Wireless communication network e.g. 5G etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Advanced Vehicle Technologies & Solutions (Vehicle connectivity (V2I, V2V, and communication technologies), Self-driving Cars, Car platooning etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Alternative Power & Energy Solutions (Alternative fuels (e.g., Biodiesel and Renewable Diesel, Natural Gas, Electric Battery, Hydrogen Fuel Cell)	<input type="radio"/>				
Intelligent Systems & Decision-Making Solutions (Data Visualization Tools and Dashboards, Fleet Management Software, Analytics Solutions, Data Mining, AI and Machine Learning)	<input type="radio"/>				
Data Security and Management (Blockchain Technology, Data Spaces, Digital Authentication, Encrypted Communications etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

* In your opinion, **how can be the impact of cutting-edge technologies, such as the ones previously described, on the following mobility service-related attributes:**

	Very Low Impact	Low Impact	Moderate Impact	High Impact	Very High Impact
User Experience / customer satisfaction / quality of service	<input type="radio"/>				
Modal integration	<input type="radio"/>				
Accessibility and proximity of transport services to people	<input type="radio"/>				
Economic efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental sustainability	<input type="radio"/>				
Affordability	<input type="radio"/>				
Equity and social inclusion	<input type="radio"/>				
Safety	<input type="radio"/>				
Security	<input type="radio"/>				

* Indicate, in your opinion, **which are the greatest barriers/challenges to foster the integration of technical innovations into new and shared mobility services** (tick all the aspects you consider)

- Regulatory hurdles
- Concerns over sharing commercially sensitive data
- Technology readiness
- Infrastructure availability
- Lack of user adoption
- Lack of technical knowledge and/or human resources
- Lack of public awareness on key benefits
- Lack of political support/funding from local governments
- Other (please specify)

* Please indicate, in your opinion, **which of the following new and shared mobility services you think could benefit the most from technical innovations** (tick all the possibilities you consider)

- Carsharing
- Bike sharing
- Moped scooter sharing
- Kick scooter sharing
- Ride-hailing
- On-demand microtransit
- Ridesharing (carpooling, vanpooling, etc.)
- Maas
- Mobility Hubs
- Other (please specify)

PROFESSIONAL BACKGROUND

Please indicate the following information about the **company / organization / government** you work for:

* Size of the company / organization / government unit you work for:

- Self-employed.
- less than 10 persons employed
- 10-49 persons employed
- 50-249 persons employed
- 250 or more persons employed

* Scope of business / activity:

- Local
- Regional
- National
- International

* Please provide the following information regarding your job position:

Country where your job is mostly based:

Position:

Years of experience:

* Is your company / organization part of the GEMINI Consortium?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

PROFESSIONAL BACKGROUND

To which of the following category/s and subcategory/s does the activity of the organisation you work for best fit? (*Tick all the categories that may identify your institution*)

GOVERNMENT AND REGULATION BODIES

- European Institution (Commission, Parliament, EU Agency, etc.)
- EU national governments
- Regional or local government
- Regulators at different levels (EU, State, Municipal...)
- Environment and regulatory bodies
- Standardization and certification body
- Cities authorities
- Public transport authorities (mostly at city/metropolitan area level)
- Other (please specify)

INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGERS AND PROVIDERS

- Public infrastructure manager
- Private parking space owners
- Charging infrastructure companies
- Other (please specify)

MOBILITY OPERATORS

- Public transport operators
- Shared mobility operators (sharing, pooling, ride hailing, etc.)
- MaaS operators
- Other (please specify)

ANCILLARY SERVICES OF MOBILITY SERVICES

- Technology providers - Data service providers
- Technology providers - Smart ticketing providers
- Energy providers
- Vehicle manufacturers
- Vehicle renters
- Other (please specify)

INVESTORS, FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS AND INSURANCE

- Financial institution (handling payments)
- Sponsoring and partnering companies
- Insurance company
- Other (please specify)

OTHER STAKEHOLDERS

- Research and Academia
- Think tank
- Consultancy firm
- Transportation Association
- User Association
- Neighbours / citizens / local communities
- NGOs
- Property developers
- Urban planners
- Smart city initiatives
- Other (please specify)

The questionnaire is completed. Thank you very much for your help.

If you are interested in the results of this study, please visit the GEMINI project website:

<https://www.geminiproject.eu/>

Please click ready to close the survey.